

Evaluation Questionnaire

[omitted for review]

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Instructions

Please answer based on your experience using the platform. Each statement should be rated on a scale from 1 to 5, where:

- (1) Strongly Disagree
- (2) Disagree
- (3) Neutral
- (4) Agree
- (5) Strongly Agree

Evaluation of the Platform

Perceived Usefulness

1. The platform helps me identify suitable quality metrics for a given evaluation scenario.
 1 2 3 4 5
2. Using the platform improves my understanding of software quality metrics and their applicability.
 1 2 3 4 5
3. The platform supports my decision-making during quality assessment activities.
 1 2 3 4 5
4. Overall, the platform is useful for evaluating blockchain-based systems.
 1 2 3 4 5

Perceived Ease of Use

5. Learning to use the platform was easy for me.
 1 2 3 4 5
6. The platform's interface is intuitive and easy to navigate.
 1 2 3 4 5
7. I can find the information I need in the platform without difficulty.
 1 2 3 4 5
8. Interacting with the platform's features feels natural and straightforward.
 1 2 3 4 5

Attitude Toward Use

9. I have a positive opinion about using the platform in evaluation tasks.
 1 2 3 4 5
10. I enjoy using the platform to explore and apply quality metrics.
 1 2 3 4 5
11. I feel confident when using the platform for quality evaluations.
 1 2 3 4 5
12. I believe using the platform contributes positively to my work or research.
 1 2 3 4 5

Behavioral Intention

13. I intend to use the platform again in future projects or studies.
 1 2 3 4 5
14. I would recommend the platform to colleagues or other researchers.
 1 2 3 4 5
15. I plan to integrate the platform into my workflow for quality assessment activities.
 1 2 3 4 5
16. I would like to continue using the platform as part of my evaluation process.
 1 2 3 4 5